

1 **Sox21 activation in head and neck cancer.**

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6 We used transcriptomics to study total total gene expression in patient-derived xenografts from humans
7 with head and neck cancer, comparing total transcription among tumors to identify genes most conserved
8 between xenograft. The approach permitted discovery of *Sox21* as a candidate target in head and neck
9 cancer in humans. In primary tumors from humans with head and neck cancer, *Sox21* was among the
10 genes transcriptome-wide most differentially expressed compared to normal tissue. A patient derived
11 xenograft system allowed discovery of an important homeobox factor with integrated validation.

12 Citations

13 1. Sandberg, M., Källström, M. and Muhr, J., 2005. Sox21 promotes the progression of vertebrate
14 neurogenesis. *Nature neuroscience*, 8(8), pp.995-1001.

15 GSE207182
16 GSE211322